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IMPACT BEHAVIOR OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES BASED ON CORRUGATED COMPOSITE CORES FILLED WITH PVC FOAM

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Introduction

- **Advantages of composite materials**

- Light-weight, high strength and stiffness to weight ratio.
- High energy absorption capacity under impact/blast loading.
- Construction potential, resistance to corrosion, recyclability and integral design.
- The ability to shape and tailor their structure to produce more aerodynamically efficient structural configurations.

- **Perspective of composite materials**

- Widely used in many military and civil applications as lightweight components in aerospace, automotive and marine applications.
- e.g. Boeing 787 is composed of up to 50% composite material by weight and 80% composite material by volume.
- Boeing 787 and Airbus A380 have a higher eco-efficiency, the lowest fuel consumption and operating costs in commercial aviation.

Experimental Procedures

• Sample preparation

- 1) The sinusoidal-shaped composite cores with varying diameter and thickness were manufactured by wrapping sheets of composite prepreg around an array of Teflon-coated steel tubes.
- 2) The skins of the sandwich structures were introduced by laying composite plies on the top and bottom surfaces of the uncured tubular array.
- 3) The entire structure was heated to 125 °c. Post-curing for 90 minutes.
- 4) The PVC foams were machined by CNC machine and filled in the curvilinear composite core structures.

• Experimental Testing

- 1) Compression tests and drop-weight impact tests at impact velocity of 5 m/s.
- 2) The displacement and force of the impact head were measured by a high speed video camera and a piezoelectric load cell respectively.

(a) corrugated core

(b) Foam filled core structures

Fig. 1 Schematic of the corrugated core and foamed filled sandwich structures

Experimental Procedures

- **Specimen and Materials**

- All-composite sandwiches (CFRP and GFRP),
- Five thicknesses between 0.25 and 1.25 mm
- Three PVC foams with nominal densities 40, 80 and 130 kg/m³

- **FE Modelling for composite and foam**

- Orthotropic elastic material
- Damage initiation – Hashin’s failure criteria
- Crushable foam with rate-dependent strain hardening
- Shear failure and tensile failure to simulate its failure mechanism, hard and ductile failure criteria

Table 1 Summary of the specimen investigated in this study

Thickness of corrugation.	C40 PVC	C80 PVC	C130 PVC
CF1	C40CF1	C80CF1	C130CF1
CF2	C40CF2	C80CF2	C130CF2
CF3	C40CF3	C80CF3	C130CF3
CF4	C40CF4	C80CF4	C130CF4
CF5	C40CF5	C80CF5	C130CF5
GF1	C40GF1	C80GF1	C130GF1
GF2	C40GF2	C80GF2	C130GF2
GF3	C40GF3	C80GF3	C130GF3
GF4	C40GF4	C80GF4	C130GF4
GF5	C40GF5	C80GF5	C130GF5

Results and Discussion

The influence of corrugation thickness

Fig. 2 Compression stress-strain traces for GFRP (GF1-GF5) corrugated cores reinforced with C80 foam based on various corrugation thicknesses.

Fig. 3 Compression stress-strain traces for CFRP (CF1-CF5) corrugated cores reinforced with C80 foam based on various corrugation thicknesses.

Fig. 4 Photograph of tested samples and FE simulation.

Results and Discussion

The influence of foam density

Fig. 5 Comparison of stress-strain traces of the corrugated GFRP cores reinforced with C40, C80 and C130 foam.

Fig. 6 Comparison of stress-strain traces of the corrugated CFRP cores reinforced with C40, C80 and C130 foam.

(a) GFRP

(b) CFRP

Fig. 7 Photograph of deformed samples based on corrugation thicknesses of 0.075 mm and C80 foam (a) GF, (b) CF.

Results and Discussion

The compressive strength and specific energy absorption

Fig. 8 Variation of compressive strength for corrugated GFRP cores reinforced with C40, C80 and C130 foam.

Fig. 9 Variation of compressive strength for corrugated CFRP cores reinforced with C40, C80 and C130 foam.

Fig. 10 The influence of foam density and corrugation thickness on SEA of the foam filled corrugated CFRP cores.

Conclusions

- The impact response of a range of all-composite sandwich structures base on corrugation core filling with PVC foam have been investigated experimentally and numerically.
- The compression strength increased with the thickness of the corrugation and density of filled PVC foam.
- The carbon fiber reinforced corrugated structures offered superior compressive properties to its glass-based counterpart, particularly at higher values of corrugation thickness. e.g. CF5C130.
- The finite element model accurately predicted the compressive response of the hybrid structures, predicting the observed failure mode in most cases successfully.
- The configuration optimization of the hybrid sandwiches was studied base on thickness of corrugation cores and density of filled foam.